

MEDICAL PLANTS OF ALTAI MOUNTAIN COUNTRY

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Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

The dataset contains a list of medicinal plants of the Altai Mountain Country. The dataset is intended to provide all interested GBIF users with information about AMC medicinal plant species, as well as further search for their growing places using the available datasets.

Geographic scope

Altai Mountainous Country (Russia, Kazakhstan, China and Mongolia)

Bibliography

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